

Analysis of Complex Structural Application Component Structures

Daminova Mashkhura Zafar kizi¹

¹ Teacher of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute

Abstract:

In this article, along with the analysis of constructions with a complex structural application component, the use, place, and semantic-syntactic properties of constructions with a complex structural application component in the sentence are analyzed. The additional meaning attached to the essence of the main expression (sentence) or a certain component of the main expression by the additional elements in the construction with the application component shows its communicative properties and the communicative functions of the application elements in the constructions with the application component characteristic forms have been studied. The famous linguists S. E. Kryuchkov and A. B. Shapiro's views and opinions about constructions with an application component are mentioned.

Keywords: complex structural construction, syntactic construction, linguistic essence, connection of sentences, distinctive feature, adjunct element, application, the rhythm.

Observations in the field of linguistics show that additional constructions can also have the characteristic of complexity. In the process of such complexity, the number of additional elements joining the main expression in the structure of the application construction should be more than one. In other words, a syntactic construction consisting of two or more attached elements is called a complex structural attached construction.

It is important to take into account the structure of the main sentence (phrase) in the application to divide the application constructions into structural groups. "The number of components that make up the structure of a simple structural application must be the same both in the main expression and in the part of the application, that is, it is required not to exceed one sentence or phrase; and the components that make up the structure of the complex structure of the application should not be less than two, both in the structure of the main expression and in the part of the application.

So, the number of basic expressions that make up complex structural constructions should be multiplied by the number of additional elements, that is, it should not be less than two. At this point, it can be said that it is appropriate to rely on their linguistic essence in the application of constructions to structural groups. The phenomenon of attachment, construction of attachment, or relationship of attachment also originates from the linguistic essence of the attachment elements aimed at giving additional meaning and content to the spoken thoughts. It seems that the application constructions with more than one such application elements should be called complex structural application constructions. Examples of such constructions include:

“My dad is a big, handsome guy. *Salt of the earth. Smart* (he does IT security for a big-name computer company). *Smushy heart.*” [Jennifer Niven “Holding up the universe” Penguin Random House UK. 2016. P.26].

In this example, the key expression is *Salt of the earth. Smart* (he does IT security for a big-name computer company). Three additional elements to “*Smushy heart*” 1. *Salt of the earth.* 2. *Smart* (he does IT security for a big-name computer company). 3. *Smushy heart* joins, completes and clarifies the main expression. As a result, a complex structural application construction is created. Here, the writer places special emphasis on the event he is describing, and in order to increase its effectiveness, he turns to a unique syntactic-stylistic event-appendix construction. This additional construction is a product of the individual style of the writer, in which special emphasis is manifested.

The quantitative increase of the additional elements added to the main sentence (expression) in the structure of the adverbial construction fulfills the following tasks:

1. Simplifies the depicted events to a certain extent;
2. It makes it easier for the reader to explain the content of these events;
3. Increases the effectiveness of the depicted events.
4. Completes and clarifies the content of the main expression.

It should be noted that the syntactic relations between the structural components of the application with a complex structure also have different forms; using words that can be related to each other in many cases; with the repetition of any lexical unit in the structure of the attachment construction; through the use of some connectives; it is represented by the syntactic-semantic integrity of the main clauses that act as the main expression.

Intonation is one of the main criteria for the emergence of an attachment relationship between the main expression (sentence) and an additional (appended) element. Many scientific research works are devoted to studying the tonal properties of the constructions. S. E. Kryuchkov comments on these specific features and emphasizes the following: “before the additional element comes a decrease in volume and a relatively large pause pronounced at a particular tempo.”

This opinion is also expressed by A. B. Shapiro, based on the statistics of Russian folk dialects, he says the following: “The rhythm of the tone also shows whether the speaker intended to say the first and the second expression” or the second whether the thought of saying the expression appeared after finishing the first expression (a large pause based on a complete lowering of the voice at the end of the first sentence). In the first case, we can talk about the connection of sentences, and in the second case, we can talk about the addition of the next one to the previous sentence.

The commonality of these scholars' views on the tonal character of the adjunct construction confirms the thesis that the uniqueness of the adjunct element appears unexpectedly in the speaker's mind. At the same time, S. E. Kryuchkov and A. B. Shapiro confirm that the uniqueness of the applied element is determined not only by its unexpected appearance in the mind of the speaker, but also by other factors. Similar opinions are expressed in a number of scientific studies.

Distinguishing the main criteria for the emergence of an attachment relationship between the components of a complex syntactic whole, A.B. Velichuk writes: "The distinctive feature of an attachment element is not determined by the time of its appearance in the speaker's mind, but by its subjective control, is defined by the independence and different planning of the lyrical theme". Continuing this point of view, the authors emphasize the following: "After the pause of the adjunctive element comes a fall in voice, if the adjunctive element is in the form of an independent sentence, the adjunctive element comes separately as an addition to the previous sentence. In such a case, a complete lowering of the sound occurs in the attached sentence. For example: compare:

"The animal kingdom has crazy names for animal groups. A zeal of zebras. A murder of crows. An unkindness of ravens. And, my favorite, an embarrassment of pandas." [Holding up the universe by Jennifer Niven, Penguin Random House UK. 2016. P.34].

The identification of application relations according to signs of unpremeditatedness and unexpectedness may raise certain objections, since the unexpected appearance of application relations is to some extent characteristic of spoken speech. At this point, Yu.V. Vannikov's comments are noteworthy, he writes: "Elementary speech experience of the speaker and an additional, unpremeditated elemental expressed sentence (main expression) equal communication and subordinate communication can be contacted via ".

In fact, the use of various adjunct constructions is related to the conscious goals of the speaker, by which an additional element can be introduced into the speech, this element serves to strengthen the previous expression or to distinguish a certain part from the whole context. does, at the same time it is given a special meaning within a complex syntactic whole. It should be noted that this structure of application communications is very common. The conducted observations showed that application links are found in written speech, both in artistic text and in scientific style, as well as in technical literature and journalism, and perform certain meaning functions.

When studying application constructions, it should be noted that they have a dual nature: application elements formed in the process of oral speech and application elements used in written speech. This thing requires special attention, because in written speech, additional elements do not appear unexpectedly, suddenly, but on the basis of specific stylistic goals. Writers use such stylistic tools in order to strengthen the expressiveness of the events described.

The definition of application relations based on semantic factors goes back to the semantic and structural independence between the application element and the main expression. The content separation of the additional elements from the first part of the main expression creates the ground for their coming in postposition (in the next place) in any additional construction. Due to the fact that it is distinguished according to logic and tone, the additional element has great syntactic potential and stylistic impact.

In short, elements with additional components serve to further complement and clarify the image of the events described in the artistic text. As a result, they provide emotionality, clarity, and imagery for the listener. At the same time, the person who is in the focus of attention creates a positive or negative feeling towards an object or an animal.

If the number of attached elements in the construction with the application component is one, such a construction is called a construction with a simple structure. They convey additional meaning and perform a certain syntactic-stylistic function.

It is observed that there are two or more additional elements that make up the constructions with the application component, such constructions are the constructions with a complex structure. Such additional elements serve to supplement and clarify the meaning of certain parts of the main expression, to strengthen the additional meaning.

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References:

1. Распопов И.П. Спорные вопросы синтаксиса. – Ростов, 1981
2. Реферовская Е.А. Лингвистические исследование структуры текста. – Л., 1983. – 215 с.
3. Реферовская Е.Д. Лингвистические исследования структуры текста. – Л., 1983.
4. Руднев А.Г. Синтаксис современного русского языка. – М., 1968.
5. Севрюгина Е.В. Отличие семантики присоединения от семантики других типов синтаксической связи. Филологические науки. Вопросы теории и практики. – Тамбов: Грамота, 2015. № 7 (49): в 2–х ч. Ч. I. – С. 158–160.
6. Сильман Т.И. Проблемы синтаксической стилистики. – Л., Просвещение, 1967. – 152 с.
7. Jennifer Niven “Holding up the universe” Penguin Random House UK. 2016. P.13,34
8. Баталова И.К. Квалификация высказываний с присоединением в аспекте актуального членения в английском языке: автореферат канд. дис. – Л., 1974.
9. Гаибова М.Т. Присоединительные конструкции и их стилистические функции в художественной прозе: автореферат канд. дис. – М., 1973.

10. Солганик Г.Я. Синтаксическая стилистика (сложное синтаксическое целое).– М., 1991. – 182 с.
11. Ванников 10.В. Синтаксис речи и синтаксические особенности русской речи. – М., 1979